

ACCOUNTING RECORD OF COMMODITY MATERIAL RESERVES THROUGH FIXED ASSETS IN A BUDGETARY ORGANIZATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6359985>

Khodjimukhamedova Shokhida Ibragimovna

Associate Professor of the
Department of Accounting and Audit
TIAME-Natsional Research University
Bobonarova Kamola Uktamjon kizi

1st year master's student
TIAME-Natsional Research University

Annotation: *Accounting record keeping are basic tools in budgetary organizations, besides intangible assets are property objects that are held by an organization for a long period of time for the purpose of using them in the process of production, performance of works, provision of services or sale of goods or for the implementation of administrative and other functions without material content. The accounting unit of intangible assets is the object of inventory. The main object of intangible assets is the sum of the rights arising from a single patent, a certificate, a contract of refusal of rights, etc. In this article, opinions and comments will be made on the accounting performance of commodity material reserves through fixed assets in a budgetary organization.*

Keywords: *Budget organizations, commodity material wealth, accounting records, basic instruments, strategic directions.*

In a budgetary organization, the conduct of accounting by means of fixed assets is the study of the correct expenditure of the estimated costs for the evasion of budgetary funds, the implementation of timely formalization and the implementation of continuous control on the basis of accounting principles, established normative – legal acts, ultimately the preparation and submission of reports. The purpose of accounting with the help of basic tools in budgetary organizations is to properly organize the accounting work carried out within the framework of the rules of procedure issued by the state and to provide users with accurate accounting information in a timely manner. In addition, the basic tools of budgetary organizations and the transfer of accounting work on their sales to the electronic system will serve to prevent corruption in the industry.

Budget accounting is the accounting of the performance of the state budget. Budget accounting covers all operations related to the execution of the state budget and provides a description of the state of the budget in this execution process. Through the budget account, the interaction of all branches of the national economy with the state budget is reflected. Through accounting, the accounts in the banking institutions reflect the monetary, income and expenses of the budget, the funds in the accounts, the funds and reserves that will be established during the execution of the budget, as well as the material values of the budgetary organizations. The revenues, costs and monetary resources of the

budget, their movement in the process of budget execution and the material values of organizations financed from the budget are direct entities of the budget account.

The main instruments in budgetary organizations, including commodity and material reserves, are material assets that are maintained in the course of normal operation for the purpose of subsequent sale and are available in the process of production, as well as in the process of production, performance of works or provision of services, or are used to carry out administrative and socio-cultural tasks. In the organization of accounting of main instruments and commodity and material reserves in budgetary organizations, the following tasks are set before the accounting of accountants:

- Reflecting material assets in the structure of commodity-material reserves in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation;
- Control over the origin of commodity and material resources, their withdrawal from the account of the organization, as well as their storage and targeted spending;
 - Follow the established standards of reserves and expenses;
 - Which must be realized in the established order;
 - Ensure correct formalization of the movement of commodity and material reserves in the documents and timely reflection in the account registers;
- Reflecting the status and behavior of commodity and material reserves in accounting accounts;
 - Formation of complete and accurate accounting information on commodity and material reserves in a timely manner.

The standard defines the procedure for maintaining the accounting records of commodity and material reserves that are relevant to legal entities in the right of ownership and reflecting them in the financial statement. Normal wrote that the standard does not apply to the accounting of financial instruments. The following Basic Rules of the account of commodity and material reserves were established:

The standard sets out the types of commodity and material reserves of organizations, the criteria by which this or that asset can be the basis for the inclusion in the composition of inventories and economic equipment. Ministries, departments, enterprises, organizations and institutions financed from the state budget submit monthly, quarterly and annual reports on the implementation of the cost estimate in the forms and terms approved by the Ministry of Finance of the country to the Ministry of Finance of the country, the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the financial authorities of Regions, Cities and districts (current) and annual report on the performance of expenditure estimates of all budgetary allocators in order to control over the progress and results of the execution of expenditures of budgetary organizations. The report is drawn up on the basis of the verified data of the analytical and syntactic account.

Conclusion. Also, one of the main functions of accounting in budgetary organizations is the processes associated with the sale of tokens. From the sentence, it is understood to correctly and accurately reflect the information that is formalized in the accounts of the accountant, to represent them in money, to ensure timely execution of the sale, to show the rule of law in the accounting documents, to ensure the accuracy of the information contained in the accounts of the accountant, and to write reports as a result.

REFERENCES:

1. Ostonakulov M. Accounting in budget organizations -T.: "Economics and Finance", 2008.
2. Kondrakov N.P., Kondrakov I.N. Accounting in budgetary organizations. - M.: Prospect, 2006.
3. Kasyanova G.Yu. Budget accounting: transition to new rules. -M.: Information center of the XXI century, 2006.
4. Ostonakulov M. Accounting for the execution of cost estimates of budget organizations. -T.: Zdravplyus / YuSAID, 2004.